

Substituted Halo Complexes of Zinc (II)

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Tetrahalo zinc(II) complexes were reacted with several substituted pyridines and quinoline in ethanolic medium. Seven, more usual tetra-coordinated and two, less common penta-coordinated mixed ligand anionic complexes were characterised by analyses, conductance and infrared spectra.

Previous work¹⁻⁴ in this laboratory revealed that d^{10} metal ions like Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) form stable four co-ordinated complexes with a variety of ligands containing different donor atoms. The relative affinities of ligand atoms for different acceptors have been summarised by Chatt *et al*⁵. In an earlier communication, we described^{6,7} a series of complexes of zinc(II) and cadmium(II) containing hetero ligand atoms. This paper describes some more compounds formed by reacting tetrahalo zinc(II) complexes with quinoline and substituted pyridines.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of Analar grade. Tetraethyl-ammonium tetrahalozincate (II) compounds were prepared following known method¹. The purity of the isolated compounds was established by estimating the metal and halogen following standard methods. In a few cases, nitrogen was also estimated.

To the suspension of tetrahalozinc(II) complexes in ethanol, the ligand was added in 1 : 2 ratio. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hr. The resulting solution on cooling deposited crystalline complexes. They were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*.

All the complexes are fairly soluble in acetone. The conductance measurements were carried out at 27° with $10^{-3}M$ solutions in acetone medium using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The analytical and conductance data are recorded in Table I.

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TABLE I

M.P., Analysis and Conductance of Substituted Halo Complexes in Zinc(II)

Complex	Colour and Form	M.P. °C	% Zinc		% Halogen		ΔM (mhos) in Acetone
			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{-Vpy}]$	White Crystalline	130	15.7	16.0	25.9	26.1	147
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnCl}_3 \cdot 4\text{-MePy}]$	White Crystalline	110	16.2	16.5	26.7	26.9	140
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnBr}_3 \cdot 2\text{-MePy}]$	White Crystalline	105	12.1	12.3	45.4	45.5	136
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnBr}_3 \cdot (3\text{-MePy})_2]$	White Crystalline	115	10.3	10.5	38.5	38.6	163
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnBr}_3 \cdot (2\text{-AmPy})]$	Light Yellow Crystalline	120	12.0	12.3	45.0	45.3	138
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnBr}_3 \cdot (2\text{-Am} \cdot 4\text{-MePy})]$	White Crystalline	128	11.6	11.9	43.9	44.2	156
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnBr}_3 \cdot \text{Q}]$	White Platelets	141	11.4	11.5	42.3	42.5	164
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnI}_3 \cdot \text{Q}]$	White Platelets	142	9.1	9.2	53.9	54.0	148
$[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnI}_3 \cdot (4\text{-Vpy})_2]$	Light Yellow Crystalline	140	8.0	8.2	48.2	48.5	160

The infrared absorption spectra of the ligands and the substituted halo complexes were recorded in the region 2000–650 cm^{-1} in Nujol mulls using a Unicam SP200 double beam spectrophotometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Divalent zinc ion has a completely filled $3d^{10}$ non-bonding shell which causes least perturbation to the shape whatever may be the preferred stereochemistry of a particular complex. This metal ion, usually, favours the formation of four coordinated tetrahedral complexes involving the use of $4s4p^3$ bonding orbitals. But the possibility of its forming penta- and hexa-coordinated compounds, utilising $4s4p^34d$ and $4s4p^34d^2$ bonding orbitals, cannot be ruled out completely.

When the tetrahalozinc(II) complexes were reacted with ligands containing nitrogen donor atoms, reaction did take place forming entirely new compounds whose form, melting point and other characteristics were completely different from those of the starting materials. Analyses of the complexes for metal and halogen reveal the formation of anionic complexes. Further, infrared spectra of the complexes show strong absorption bands of both the tetraethyl ammonium ion and the ligands. The compounds isolated were therefore definitely

substituted anionic complexes of zinc(II). The shifting and/or splitting of ligand absorption bands as were seen in the complexes were indicative of definite metal-ligand bonding and discussion of the absorption bands of the free ligands and their modification on being bonded to the metal will be taken up later on. In acetone medium, the Λ_M values for 1 : 1 electrolytes are usually round about 150 mhos and hence the values for Λ_M recorded in Table I, show that these complexes are all 1 : 1 electrolytes and this observation is in conformity with their formulae.

The complexes having the formulae $[\text{Et}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnX}_3\text{L}]$ where the hetero ligand atom L is quinoline, 2-methyl, 4-methyl, 4-vinyl, 2-amino or 2-amino 4-methyl pyridine retain the original four-coordination found in the tetrahalo compounds. The tribromobis-(3-methylpyridine) zinc(II) and the triiodo bis-(4-vinyl pyridine) zinc(II) complexes are interesting on account of their penta-coordination. We had earlier shown that zinc(II) is pentacoordinated in the complexes $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][\text{ZnBr}_3(4\text{MePy})_2]$ ⁶ and $[\text{Zn}(4\text{MePy})_3(\text{CNS})_2]$ ⁸. A few more examples where the zinc ion is five-coordinated are aquo bis-(acetyl-acetonato) zinc(II)⁹; dichloro(-terpyridyl) zinc(II)¹⁰ and bis-(acetylacetonato) (4-methyl pyridine) zinc(II)¹¹.

There are two possible structures for penta-coordinated complexes, *viz.*, trigonal bipyramid or a square pyramid. Taking into account the nature of the hybrid orbitals involved in bonding, Daudel and Bucher¹² indicated the preferred stereochemical shapes under different conditions. According to Gillespie¹³ for transition elements, with d^0 and d^{10} configurations, the trigonal bipyramidal shape, determined by interactions between the 5 electron pairs in the valence shell, is preferred for a five-coordinate complex. However, only X-ray crystallographic studies can elucidate the exact preferred structure.

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